

EMPLOYEE WELFARE AND WORK COMMITMENT IN NIGERIA PUBLIC SECTOR: A STUDY OF NESREA SOUTH WEST ZONE

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Abstract: This study is on employee welfare and employee commitment in a public service organization: a study of NESREA South West Zone, Nigeria. The main objective is to; find out the welfare packages enjoyable/payable to employees of NESREA South West Zone. The data gathered from 154 respondents using the five-point Likert-Style Rating Scale questionnaire were thematically presented with the aid of tables and descriptive research technique was adopted accordingly. The method of data analysis used was the Z-test research technique. Interestingly, study found that there are spelt out welfare packages in Public Service Rule (PSR) for all Federal Civil Service workers' but even though employees of NESREA South West Zone are enjoying their welfare packages stipulated in PSR, study revealed that all the staff members may not enjoy these privileges at same time, at various times staff members of the organization have benefited. Study recommended among others that to fully motivate and secure staff commitment, welfare provisions as stipulated in PSR need to be duly implemented to arouse commitment, loyalty and honesty towards improved performance in the organization.

Keywords: Employee welfare, work commitment, welfare package and public sector.

1. INTRODUCTION

Background to the Study

The welfare of employees is a fundamental aspect of Human Resource Management (HRM) as it is vital to influencing commitment to the actualization of goal in both private and public organizations. Marzullo (2018) confirms that committed employees are an asset to an organization as they are supportive and more productive than non-committed employees. Simiyu, Agala, Kinuthia, Nkoiboni, Gateru, Galgalo, Kioko, Ondari (2009) pointed out the important of employee commitment to the functioning of the entire organization, According to them: employees commitment is paramount, since it is due to high commitment of employees that HRM of any organization could achieve positive results, in terms of increased effectiveness, while low employees commitment could leads to poor results of the functioning of the entire organization.

There is no doubt that employees will commit their strengths and talents to utilizing available resources toward the actualization of the organization goal, if employees are not denied their expected welfare package or facilities. However, there have been great expectations at all levels, that employees welfare be taken seriously in order to enhance employees commitment, but in reality, meeting or satisfying employees welfare in public organizations in Nigeria appears to remain a mere rhetoric or a theoretical deliberation that is yet to receive adequate attention. Particularly, the Nigeria's situation since

independence in 1960 showed that no matter how a country is richly blessed in natural resources, that country will remain a sleeping giant until she is able to effectively manage, develop and mobilize her human resources toward actualization of National Developmental Goals (Udofia, 2012). Nevertheless, this may be difficult where employees welfare are neglected.

Maugo (2013) asserts that people are the most important drivers of any organization, and organizations are reliant upon their human assets to survive and thrive. According to Dongs and Egbunu (2013), men that makes up the employees are expected to be strategically fashioned, positioned, structured and pattern to dream, conceptualize ideas, initiate desires, visualize objectives and actualize the set goals. Yet, there is consensus among scholars that some organizations have problem finding the resources to invest in the training and development of employees, while some have problem in coping with changing employment laws and choose to ignore it. No doubt that such situation can negatively affect employees commitment. Hence, the needs for an indebt reexamine welfare of employees and how it affects employee's commitment in public service organizations in the country and to proffer durable solutions. Primarily, therefore, this study examines the effect of welfare on employees commitment in National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency (NESREA) South West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

NESREA is a federal public service organization, a parastatal of the Federal Ministry of Environment, established by the National Environmental Standards and Regulations Enforcement Agency Act 25, 2007. The Agency is charged with the responsibility of enforcing all environmental laws, guidelines, policies, standards and regulations in Nigeria. It also has the responsibility to enforce compliance with provisions of international agreements, protocols, conventions and treaties on the environment. Its vision is to ensure cleaner and healthier environment for all Nigerians while, its mission is to inspire personal and collective responsibility in building an environmentally-conscious society for the achievement of sustainable development in Nigeria (Ladan, 2012). Some of the routine activities or functions of NESREA include: compliance monitoring of facilities or industries to ensure that their operations are environmentally friendly, investigations into public complaints on environmental nuisance, sensitization/awareness creation on sound environment (NESREA Newsmagazine, 2012). The welfare of the employees of NESREA is paramount and is expected to be properly handled or managed, if they must be committed to the vision, mission and mandate of organization in the South West Geopolitical Zone and not compromise standards in the process of carrying out their environmental regulatory and enforcement responsibilities.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Conceptual Clarification

Public Service Organization

There are no universal definitions of Public Service Organization (PSO), due to differences in its concept and scope from country to country. In Nigeria, public service organizations are mandatory institutions under the Constitution of the Federal Republic (CFR, 2011) as amended, Chapter VI: Executive, Part 1 (D) and Part II (C) provides for a public service at the federal and state levels of government. The PSO in Nigeria is made up of the following:

- (1) The Civil Service, which is often referred to as the core service and is composed of line ministries and extra-ministerial agencies; and
- (2) The public bureaucracy, which is composed of the enlarged public service, including the following:
 - (a) Services of the state and national assembly;
 - (b) The judiciary
 - (c) The armed forces
 - (d) The police and other security agencies
 - (e) Paramilitary services (immigration, customs, prisons, etc.)
 - (f) 'Parastatals' and agencies including social service, commercially oriented agencies, regulatory agencies, educational institutions and research institutes.

In addition, Otodo, Omole and Mamser cited by Nkoli (2011) conceived parastatals are Federal and State corporations like the Nigerian Railway Corporation, Housing Corporation, Port Authorities, Air and Sea, Crude oil and Solid mineral,

Ventures and Transportation undertakings. Others include the Power Holding Company of Nigeria, Water Corporation, Nigerian Television Authority (NTA), Federal and State Radio Corporations, the Nigerian Postal Service (NIPOST), Federal and State Waste Management Board; the Banking industry, among others. These parastatals are supposed to provide certain essential services to members of the public even if they are unable to make profits or at least break even.

Generally, Olufemi (2015) clarifies that PSO are built up to execute the policy of the legislature so as to empower the administration to achieve its political, financial and social objectives. In the process of the public servants performing this executive function, they are expected to be efficient and effective in the course of discharging their responsibilities. Their performance which is expressed in terms of quantity of goods and services goes along way to determining the economic growth and development of the country. In public organizations the civil servants or public servants are the employees, while government is their employer.

Concept of Employees

According to Grimsley (2018), employees are people who are been managed by the Human Resource Management (HRM) of an organization, be it private or public, in order to achieve set goals. Merriam-Webster (2018) defines *employee* as one employed by another usually for wages or salary and in a position below the executive level. According to Employment New Zealand (ENZ, 2018), *employees* are people who have agreed to be employed to work for some form of payment under a contract of service. Payment under a contract of service can include wages, salary, commission and piece rates. Online Free Dictionary (OFD, 2018) conceived *employees* are often called public or civil servants working in a variety of fields such as teaching, sanitation, environment, health care, management, and administration in public service organizations or institutions. Employees are expected to enjoy job security, housing facilities, healthcare services, promotion and educational opportunities and others benefits, comprehensive medical insurance coverage, and pension as well as other benefits often not provided in comparable positions in private employment.

Concept of Welfare

According to Human Resource Management Practice Guide (HRMPG, 2018) and Projects4MBA (2018), *welfare* can be defined as the efforts to make life worth living for workmen or employees. *Welfare* is a comprehensive term including various services, benefits and facilities offered to employees by the employers. Through such generous fringe benefits the employer makes life worth living for employees.” Employees welfare includes *anything that is done for the comfort and improvement of employees* and is provided over and above the wages. Employees’ welfare helps in keeping the morale and motivation of the employees high so as to retain the employees for longer duration. The welfare measures are not only in monetary terms but in any kind or forms. Employees’ welfare include: monitoring of working conditions, provision or creation of healthcare infrastructure, insurance against disease, accident for the workers and their families.

Employee welfare entails all those activities of employer which are directed towards providing the employees with certain facilities and services in addition to wages or salaries. As Ijeoma (2018) have it to say, employees now associate good employer and jobs as those that promote steady job, give them high wages, salary, bonuses and promote decent conditions, provides opportunity for generous welfare/benefits. If denied employees, is likely to have negative effect on their commitment to duty.

Concept of Employees Commitment

As Marzullo (2018) put it, employees’ commitment is refers to how devoted employees are in the organization or company; the bond employees have with their place of work or their organization or the attitude of aligning with the objectives and values of the organization. Hence, according to Wainwright (2018), employees who are committed to their organization generally feel a connection with organization and goal of the organization. The value of such employees is, they tend to be more determined in their work, show relatively high loyalty and more proactive in offering their support to the organization.

More elaborately, Meyer and Allen, Wiener, Scholl, Glisson & Durick, O’Reilly & Caldwell, Rhodes & Steers as cited in Coetzee (2005); conceived that commitment reflects at least three general themes: affective attachment to the organization, the perceived costs associated with leaving it and the obligation to remain with it. These three approaches are referred to as *affective, continuance* and *normative* commitment.

Empirical Studies on Employee Welfare and Employees Commitment

Empirically, many scholars has made valuable contributions through their studies on topics related to welfare and employees commitment, but none of them has the same focus with this present study, due to their varying interests. For instance, Odeku and Odeku (2015) study titled *"Importance of the Welfare Facilities in the Workplace: Issues in Perspectives"*, examined the importance of welfare facilities and services to the workforce and the need for an organization to ensure they provide statutory welfare schemes and non-statutory welfare schemes for their employees. The article accentuates the importance of implementation of welfare schemes and the consequences for failure of implementation.

The importance of welfare schemes, facilities and services are increasingly being agitated for by workers and organized labour. Welfare schemes are recognized by international labour organizations and they all enjoin each member state to the organization to ensure implementation. Employees deserve more than only salaries or wages, hence the argument for provision and improvement of existing welfare facilities in the workplaces. The benefits of welfare facilities are twofold; the employees benefit and at the same time it serves as an impetus for efficiency and effectiveness in the chain of productive activities in the workplaces. It is a win-win situation. The employers will however benefit more because efficiency and effective production will lead to huge output which would invariable impact on the profit and margins of the organization and make it a perpetually sustainable venture.

Similarly, Robles (2018) work titled *"Influence of Employee Benefits on Employee Satisfaction: A Case a of Five Stars Hotels in Nairobi"* reveals that employee remuneration is not just about salaries but is also concerned with long term benefits such as pension. Pension can enhance employee satisfaction and loyalty. It revealed that paid time off contributes to employee satisfaction in the organization, having flexible work schedules increases employee satisfaction and loyalty as well. Leave benefit and family-friendly benefits increases employee satisfaction. Employees also agreed that leave allows for personal rest and social activities, and finally the results showed that employees are overall satisfied with their employment benefits. The study concluded there is clear evidence that five stars hotels in Nairobi uses various forms of employees' financial benefits such as allowances as recognition strategy to show the value of employees at work. It can also be concluded that retirement benefits enhance employee's satisfaction and loyalty. Social benefits also influence employees satisfaction by a great extent, being family friendly benefits packages, paid time off and flexible work schedules considered the most important for employees in the organization.

It recommended that since the hospitality industry is grabbing a biggest share of the market, giving a wide variety of options to Kenyan population to be employees in this hospitality industry therefore it is important to explore more about fringe benefits offered to the employees for this particular sector. This study only focused on influence of employee benefits on employee satisfaction. Therefore, more research needs to be done to determine other employee benefits that affect employee satisfaction. The study should also be conducted in other organizations specially the ones related with the service industry.

An empirical study carried out by Lagat, Mutai, and Kosgey (2014) on *"Importance of Employee Welfare and Performance: The Case of the UASU at Edgerton University, Kenya"* disclosed that Trade Unions play a key role in enhancing employee welfare and performance in organizations. In Kenya, the Universities' Academic Staff Union (UASU) is a trade union for academic staff in all the public universities, with chapters in every university and whose objects include ensuring better welfare for its members. Through a cross-sectional survey, this study examined the contribution of the UASU to employee welfare and the extent of its effects on employee performance. The respondents provided information regarding the contribution of the activities of the UASU to employee welfare and their influence on employee performance. Results indicated that the UASU had different but positive impacts on the variables affecting employee welfare and, consequently, employee performance. In descending order of importance, maternity, pension, housing and medical schemes were some of the benefits from the activities of the UASU. However, availability of recreational facilities received least attention from the UASU. It recommended that UASU should, be maintained and strengthened to further improve on quality delivery of products and services in the University by its members.

Important information from the empirical work of Odeku and Odeku (2014) titled *"In Pursuit of the Employees' Welfare in the Workplace: Issues in Perspectives"* primarily investigated how existing labour laws in Nigeria are serving as protective mechanisms toward the welfare of the employees in the workplace. It found that employees are of the perception that although capital is provided by the employers, they are the main resource used to bring about output and production which eventually bring back the investment and huge dividends to the employers. Employees are important to the progress of any

organization so, they should be kept happy and provided for with sustainable wages, welfare packages and other incentives which are not always given. It is therefore not unusual to see labour unrest as a result of complaints of poor welfare provisions and services to the workers. Therefore, it recommended that employers are enjoined to, at all times, take innovative proactive approach to the issue of staff welfare. Even if they are prescribed in law, the employer can exceed what the law prescribed especially if the workers are doing their bits and growing the business through their massive hard work and loyalty. The employees should not be outrageous and unnecessarily difficult in their approach towards negotiation for improved welfare in the workplace. Both parties have stakes in the business hence; they should sit down and work out an acceptable modality that will be beneficial to both.

Interestingly, Oyewobi (2013) work titled "*Influence of Public Service Motivation on Job Satisfaction and Organizational Commitment of Quantity Surveyors in Nigerian Public Service*" investigated the impact of Public Service Motivation (PSM) on job satisfaction and organizational commitment amongst Quantity Surveyors (QSs). It sampled the opinions of QSs in Nigeria Federal Ministries and Parastatals and revealed that QS in public service are more satisfied with their job when adequate recognition is given and opportunities for advancement are encouraged. Showing that, there is strong positive relationship existed between job satisfaction and public interest and also between organizational commitment and self-sacrifice. It therefore, recommended that advancement opportunity in career progression and professional development such as in-house training should be encouraged to improve quality service delivery and that PSM should be seen as a vital instrument that could be employed to search for individuals who are best suited and ready to render selfless service for public work.

Moreover, result from the empirical research carried out by Irefin and Mechanic (2014) on "*Effect of Employee Commitment on Organizational Performance in Coca Cola Nigeria Limited Maiduguri, Borno State*" shows among others that: employee commitment is high; there is a fairly high relationship between employee commitment and organizational performance; there is also a very high relationship between employee commitment and employees' turnover. In view of this, it was recommended that: the management should hire employees who are likely to become linked to the organization; management should create clear and realistic job and organizational previews.

On a broader note, an empirical work by Agada and Zeb-Obipi (2018) on "*Workplace Social Infrastructure And Employee Commitment: A Literature Review*" examined how dimensions of workplace social infrastructure such as staff, guest house/club, housing scheme, and transportation facilities influence normative, affective, and continuance commitment. It found that: state of the art staff guest house/club enhances normative commitment; well-planned housing scheme enhances commitment; transportation facilities also boost continuance commitment. It argued that adequate and functional workplace social infrastructure boost and sustains employees' commitment. It recommended that organizations should build, establish and equip staff guest houses and sporting clubs with facilities to cater for the recreational needs of their employees as it will boost job satisfaction and intention to stay; management should provide well-furnished staff quarters, housing estates and subsidized residential houses with good pipe-borne water and electricity to lessen employees' financial stress associated with hiring or buying residential houses; and that management should issue car loans or provide official cars, staff buses and monitoring vehicles to ensure the safety and transit security of their staff as well as cater for their transportation costs to give them a sense of belonging. As all these will lead to organizational members' bonding with the organization; and enhance employee commitment.

Employee Welfare packages In South West Nigeria

Non-Monetary welfare enjoyable by Employees of NESREA South West as stipulated in PSR.

S/N	Types of Leave	Rule
(1)	Annual Leave	Annual Leave is the absence of an officer from duty for a <i>Annual leave</i> period specified in Rule 100203 as may be authorized by a superior officer.
		Annual Leave shall be granted to an officer in accordance with his grade level as follows: (a) GL 07 and above (30 calendar days); (b) GL04-06 (21 calendar days); (c) GL 03 and Below (14 calendar days).
		100202; 100203

(2)	Proportionate Leave	<p>(a) An officer who joins the Federal Public Service during the course of the Leave Year will not normally be granted an annual leave but a proportionate leave. The proportionate leave allowance shall be based on the number of earned leave days.</p> <p>(b) Officers who attend courses of instruction/training over a period of six months shall be entitled to proportionate leave for the period they put in service.</p> <p>(c) An officer who is retiring within the period of Leave-Earning Service shall be entitled to proportionate leave.</p>	100212
(3)	Casual Leave	<p>Casual Leave is the absence of an officer from duty for a short period not exceeding an aggregate of 5 working days within a leave year as may be authorized by a superior officer. The casual leave shall only be granted after an officer has exhausted his/her annual leave. Casual leave is deductible in advance or arrears of earned leave.</p> <p>A maximum of seven days casual leave shall be granted in any leave year. Casual leave in excess of seven days in any leave year may be granted only by the Permanent Secretary/Head of Extra-Ministerial Office.</p>	100214; 100215
(4)	Sick Leave	Sick Leave is the absence of an officer from duty on account of ill-health as authorized by a Healthcare Provider.	100216
(5)	Maternity Leave	<p>Maternity Leave is the authorised absence from duty of a serving female officer granted by a superior officer on account of pregnancy covering the prenatal and postnatal periods.</p> <p>A female staff that is pregnant is entitled to 16 weeks maternity leave at a stretch beginning not less than 4 weeks from the expected date of delivery with full pay. A medical certificate showing the expected date of confinement must be presented not less than two months before that date. The annual leave for that year will, however, be regarded as part of the maternity leave. Where this annual leave has already been enjoyed before the grant of maternity leave that part of the maternity leave equivalent to the annual leave will be without pay.</p> <p><i>Time off for Nursing mothers:</i> Any female officer who is nursing a child shall be granted two hours off-duty every day. This facility shall be granted up to a maximum period of six months from the date she resumes duty from maternity leave.</p>	100217; 100218; 100219
(6)	Study Leave	<p>Study Leave is the leave granted to a confirmed serving officer to undertake an approved course of study within or outside the country.</p> <p>There are three types of study leave:</p> <p>(a) <i>In-service Training:</i> Officers shall be granted in-service training for a period not exceeding two years with normal emoluments, allowances and course fees. The period of study shall count towards gratuity and pension,</p> <p>(b) <i>Study leave with pay:</i> Study leave with pay shall be granted to an officer with normal emoluments and allowances. The duration of study leave with pay shall not exceed two years. If, however, an officer has a carry-over, the period of extension shall not be more than one year. The period of extension shall also attract pension, right of emoluments and allowances.</p>	100223; 100224

		(c) <i>Study leave without pay</i> : Officers on study leave without pay are not entitled to emoluments and allowances.	
(7)	Leave on Compassionate Ground	An officer may be allowed special leave from duty on full pay on compassionate ground for a period up to two weeks for burial of spouse/child/parents/parents of spouse.	100230
Source: PSR (2009).			

Monetary Welfare Package Payable to Employees of NESREA South West as Stipulated in PSR

S/N	Types of Welfare package	Rule	
(1)	Kilometres Allowance	Kilometre allowance shall be paid to newly appointed officers reporting to their duty station; retiring officers from duty; officers undertaking responsibility using their cars and on transfer or posting at the rates specified in their extant circular.	130103
(2)	Disengagement Allowance	Disengagement allowance shall be paid to an officer proceeding on retirement from service at uniform rates of 5% of annual basic emolument plus authorized allowance as stated in Rule 130103.	130104
(3)	Hotel Accommodation Allowance;	Officers on posting, transfer or on assumption of duty on new appointment at their new station, different from their city/town of domicile shall be entitled to transport fare for self, spouse and a maximum of four children. In addition, they shall be eligible for hotel accommodation for the first 28 days or an allowance for the first 28 days in lieu of hotel accommodation, as specified in the extant circular.	130105
(4)	Duty Tour Allowance	Duty Tour Allowance is granted to enable officers pay for lodging and feeding expenses during official tours duly approved by the official authority. The rates applicable are as may be specified in the extant circular.	130106
(5)	Transport and Local Running Allowance	(a) All officers are entitled to airfare depending on the exigencies and with the approval of the Accounting Officer. (b) Transport allowance shall be paid to all officers when travelling to towns and cities where air transport services do not exist at the rates of N20.00 per kilometre. (c) For the purpose of local running, officers shall be granted 30% of their duty tour allowance in addition to airport taxi, at the prevailing rates.	130107
(6)	Estacode Supplementation Allowance	Where the cost of accommodation or hotel expenses of an officer travelling abroad is met by the host Government or institution, such officer shall be entitled to estacode supplementation allowance as follows: (a) where the donor providing the training as a form of technical assistance to Nigeria also provides free boarding and lodging, the officer concerned shall be entitled to 10 per cent of his/her appropriate estacode for the whole duration of his course; in other words, no full estacode for the first 28 days is payable; (b) Where the donor providing the training provides free lodging alone, the officer concerned throughout the whole duration of his/her course shall be paid 40% of his estacode to meet boarding and incidental expenses (full estacode for first 28 days not payable);	130110

		(c) Where the donor provides free lodging plus cash allowance, the officer will claim the cash difference between the cash payment by the donor Government and the 30 per cent of his/her appropriate estacode (no full estacode for the first 28 days), (d) However, where the donor merely gives the officer cash towards the cost of boarding and lodging and other incidentals, the officer is entitled to receive the difference between the total cash paid him/her, by the host Government, and the estacode rate payable to him by Nigerian Government, i.e. he/she will receive full estacode for the first 28 days and 30 per cent of his/her appropriate estacode for the remaining period of the course, less the cash payment made to him/her by the donor.	
(7)	Warm Clothing Allowance	(a) An officer who is required by Government to proceed to a foreign country on duty or on an approved course of instruction will be eligible for a warm clothing allowance as may be specified in the extant circular.	130112
(8)	Local Course Allowance	(a) Local Course of instruction is: a course which an officer takes locally in Nigeria but outside his/her station. (b) An officer attending a local course of institution at any Federal Training Centre, University or other approved Public Service Training Institutions is eligible for Training Allowance as follows: (i) For courses exceeding 28 days and where boarding lodging are not provided by the Training Institutions concerned, officers will be entitled-to 30% of the Duty Tour Allowance for the 1 SI 28 days and such rates as may be specified in the relevant circulars thereafter. (ii) For courses not exceeding 28 days and where board and lodging are not provided by the Training Institute, officers shall be entitled to 50% of the Duty Tour Allowance.	130113
(9)	Resettlement Allowance;	Resettlement allowance previously known as disturbance Allowance not an emolument. It is granted in compensation for out of pocket expenses not covered by other regulations, but which are incurred by the officers in the course of transfer as defined in Rule 130134. For the purpose of this Chapter "transfer" includes the following: (i) transfer from one station to another during a tour of service; (ii) transfer from one station to another on return from leave; (iii) transfer or secondment from the service of another Government in the Federation; Resettlement Allowance shall be paid at the rate of 2% of an Officer's annual emolument.	130132; 130133; 130134
Source: PSR (2009).			

Theoretical Framework

The commitment theories includes the side-bet period theory, middle affective dependence period theory and social exchange theory are relevant in understanding employees commitment. Hence, they serve as theoretical frame or explanations to further add relevance to this study.

Side-Bet Period Theory

Irefin and Mechanic (2014) citing from Howard Becker's, writes that the side-bet theoretical approach was one of the earliest attempts to study a comprehensive framework about employee commitment from perspective of the individual's relationship with the organization. The relationship between employee and organization are based on the "contract" of economic exchange behaviour, committed employees are committed because they have totally hidden or somewhat hidden investments, "side-bets," they have made by remaining in a given organization. If someone left, the investments of "side-bet" will be claimed hardly. The term "side-bets" refers to the accumulation of investments valued by the individual. It

argues that over a period of time certain costs accrue that make it more difficult for the person to disengage from a consistent pattern of activity, namely, maintaining membership in the organization.

This theoretic approach claimed that a close connection between employee commitment and employees' voluntary turnover behavior exist. It believes that commitment should be measured by evaluating the reasons, if any that would cause a person to leave his organization. *The critique of the side-bet period theory*: The theory failed to identify which kind of investment an employees could have invested in an organization that would keep them and motivate them to remain connected or belted with their organization, even when welfare is denied them. The question is, are the employees part of the company by share that will make them to remain with the organization? This was not identified. Employee's retention does not only come from economic factors but also affective or social influence and the later is more significant. Hence, it is not applicable in public service organization especially in Nigeria where civil or public servants who are employees of government have no any single investment in the organization where they work.

Middle Affective-Dependence Period Theory

Irefin and Mechanic (2014) unfolded the second period of employee commitment was advanced by Porter, Monday and Steers (1982). The focus of commitment shifted from tangible side-bets to the psychological attachment one had to the organization. The affective dependence school attempted to describe commitment as a kind of attitude centered but "economic-contract". Employee's retention does not only come from economic factors but also affective influence and the later is more significant. Accordingly, commitment was defined by Porter and his followers as "the relative strength of an individual's identification with and involvement in a particular organization". Then they claimed employee commitment was combined with three parts: "Strong Acceptance", "Participation" and "Loyalty". The exchange theory was established as the main explanation for the process of commitment.

Social Exchange Theory

Maugo (2013) citing from Curry and Crede (2005), postulated that the concept employee commitment is best defined through the deployment of the social exchange theory. The social exchange theory is grounded in an economic model of human behaviour whereby interactional processes between individuals are persuaded by a desire to increase rewards and decrease losses. The social exchange theory's point of departure is that the relationships that provide more rewards and diminish costs earn enduring reciprocal trust and attraction. For instance, if employees are more efficient and effective in executing assigned duties they cut costs of not being productive and employers that are generous in rewarding and supporting their employees eliminate poor performance as a result of dissatisfaction of employees. Thus, the social exchange process entails both material benefits and psychological benefits that include status, loyalty and approval.

There is a behavioural correlation between commitment and turnover in the organization. For organizations to be effective they depend on the employees' loyalty which is a variable that is also affected by the willingness and degree of engagement in the task assigned to them and beyond the required role. The social exchange theorists believed that an employee's commitment to an organization is influenced by the organization's commitment to employee. From the perspective of the employee-employer relationship, social exchange theory suggests that employees respond to perceived favourable working conditions by behaving in ways that benefit the organization and/or other employees. Equally, employees retaliate against dissatisfying conditions by engaging in negative work attitudes, such as absenteeism, lateness, tardiness or preparing to quit the organization. It is therefore, expected that employees who perceive their working conditions to be negative and distressing, would reciprocate with negative work attitudes such job dissatisfaction, low morale and reduced organizational commitment, while those who perceive the workplace conditions as positive and challenging would reciprocate with positive work attitudes, such as high commitment, job satisfaction and low turnover.

Among the above theoretical explanations, the social exchange theory better applies to this study. Why? It emphasizes on the employee-employer relationship, It suggests that employees respond to perceived favourable working conditions by behaving in ways that benefit the organization and/or other employees. Equally, employees retaliate against dissatisfying conditions by engaging in negative work attitudes, such as absenteeism, lateness, tardiness or preparing to quit the organization. This has been the situation in most public sector organization in Nigeria where employees shows 'I do not care' attitude towards their job as a result of poor welfare and unfavorable working conditions.

Empirically, evidence from Olufemi (2015) gave credence to the social exchange theory of commitment where he reveals that poor welfare such as meager income remunerated, poor condition of work experience by employees/workers in the public sector organization: in Nigeria has the following implications on their attitudes (commitment) towards work in a workplace: *lateness to work; absenteeism at work* - some time by pretending to be sick; *office trading by public servants* - survival strategies, some public officials may turn to teaching, consulting for development agencies, while other prefer to concentrate their activities on interventions - especially capacity building projects - that benefit from donor funded allowances to help themselves and their family. Hence, Ijeoma (2018) theorizes that since human capital are the lifeblood of any organization and therefore depends to a large extent on the quality of those who perform its task leading to set objectives as well as conditions which affect their mental and physical health. The employees whose services are engaged should be made to be satisfied with their jobs. To this end various welfare packages should be employed to ensure the attainment of organizational goals. No wonder, Odeku and Odeku (2014) wrote that both employers and employees have stakes in business of any organization, acceptable modality that will be beneficial.

3. METHODOLOGY

Population of the Study

For the purpose of this study, the employees of NESREA South West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria are the population of interest. The target population is 158 employees which represent the entire population of the Technical (Enforcement) Officers, Administration and Account Officers in Ekiti, Ondo and Oyo state offices as shown in Table 1

Table 1: Population Distribution

S/No	NESREA South West Offices	Department	Population Characteristics	Population No
1	Ekiti Office	Technical	Technical (Enforcement) Officers	20
		Administration & Finance	Administration and Account Officers	11
		Administration & Finance	Administration and Account Officers	15
2	Ondo Office	Technical	Technical (Enforcement) Officers	37
3	. Oyo/Ibadan Zonal Office	Technical	Technical (Enforcement) Officers	55
		Administration & Finance	Administration and Account Officers	20
Total				158

Source: NESREA HR (2021).

Sampling Technique

In this study, stratified random sampling method was used. According to investopedia(2019) stratified random sampling is a method of sampling that involves the division of a population into smaller sub-groups known as strata. Strata are formed passed on members shared characteristics. Stratified random sampling has three main benefits: it: increases a sample's statistical efficiency, provides adequate data for analyzing the various subpopulations. The study population was derived on the basis of various functions or divisions within NESREA Offices in Ekiti, Ondo and Oyo state domicile in South West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria which includes Technical and Administration and Finance Department. These ensured holistic participation or representation across the various functions or divisions of the organization.

Sample Size of Study

How large a sample should be is always a function of the variation in the population parameters under study and also the estimating precision or accuracy needed by the researcher. Some of the principles which influence choice of sample size include among others: it must be able to provide estimation precision. The greater the desired precision of the estimate, the larger the sample must be. The narrower the interval range, the larger the sample must be. The higher the confidence level in the estimate, the larger the sample must be. The greater the number of subgroups of interest within a sample and also the greater the sample size must be, as each sub group must meet minimum sample size requirements.

However, for this study the entire population from the various departments of NESREA Offices in South West Geopolitical Zone including that of Ekiti, Ondo, and Oyo State Office is 158 staff all together. This will be adopted holistically as the sample size, since all the targeted population is not too large. Hence, the total sample size that considered while collecting data was 158.

Table 2: Sample Size and Percentage

S/No.	NESREA South West Offices	Department	Population Characteristics	Population No	Sample size	Percentage of the entire population
1	Ekiti Office	Technical	Technical (Enforcement) Officers	20	20	13%
		Administration & Finance	Administration and Account Officers	11	11	6%
2	Ondo Office	Technical	Technical (Enforcement) Officers	37	37	24%
		Administration & Finance	Administration and Account Officers	15	15	9%
3	Oyo/Ibadan Zonal Office	Technical	Technical (Enforcement) Officers	55	55	35%
		Administration & Finance	Administration and Account Officers	20	20	13%
Total				158	158	100%

Source: Author's Calculation (2021)

Sources of Data Collection

There are two major sources of data collection, primary and secondary. However, this study relied on both. The secondary data were derived from books, journals, government gazettes/documents, NESREA websites and magazines with relevant information that was useful to the study. The primary data were collected from the employees who are working in NESREA South West Geopolitical Zone Offices in Ekiti, Ondo and Oyo/Ibadan along with their views and suggestions through structured questionnaire method to provide answers to the study.

Method of Data Collection

For the purpose of this study, the researcher visited NESREA office physically to assess some relevant government gazettes/documents, magazines used search engines retrieve and assess books, journals as well will visit NESREA websites to get relevant secondary materials or information that was useful to the study and to support the primary data. Using the primary method, the researcher will be depending on the five-point Liker-Style rating scale method of questionnaire to obtain information from respondents.

Method of Data Analysis

The data was gathered from responses. The questionnaire was analyzed using two types of statistical methods: (i) The percentage method denoted by $X/(N) \times 100/1$ (this will be used to determine the percentage of responses from the respondents that was presented in tabular forms). Where: X= frequency of respondents and N= total number of respondents. (ii) The data gathered from the questionnaire were presented using tables and analyzed by employing the Z-test statistic. The Z-test formula is given as thus:

$$Z = \frac{\bar{X} - \mu}{\sigma / \sqrt{N}}$$

Where \bar{X} = mean observation

σ = Standard deviation of the observation

μ = a constant

N = number of observation

Table 3: Analysis of Data Using E-views 7 software

Variable	Category	Mean	Df	SD	Z-value	Prob.	Remark
Welfare packages	NESREA South West	56.7	2.38	7.33	8.05*	0.02	Sig.
Employees' Commitment	NESREA South West	33.9	2.38	2.89	11.32*	0.00	Sig.
Significant at 0.05 Level							

Source: Author's Computation, 2021

The degree of freedom is given as: $(r - 1)(c - 1)$; where $r = 4$, $c = 2$.

$$(4 - 1)(3 - 1) = 3 \times 1 = 3.$$

$$Df = 3 \text{ at } 5\% \text{ level of significance} = 2.38$$

Interpretation of Results

From table3, the Welfare packages variable, the mean within the period of the study was 56.7. The standard deviation value was 7.33. The z-value of 8.05 indicates that the obtained result is highly significant. Likewise, the probability value which was 0.02 lends credence to the statistical significance of the obtained result. For Employees' commitment, the mean within the period of this study was 33.9. The standard deviation value was 2.89. The z-value of 11.32 indicates that the obtained result is highly significant. Likewise, as indicated by the probability value which was 0.05 lend credence to the statistical significance of the obtained result. In drawing decision based on the obtained results using the z-values obtained, we recall that there is a strong relationship between Employee Welfare and Work commitment

Decision: From the computation results obtained, we observed that the calculated result is greater than the table result at 5% level of significance i.e. $2.38 > 1.30$. This shows that Welfare has significant effect on employees' commitment in NESREA South West Geopolitical Zone of Nigeria.

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